

Hypothetical explanation of light refraction and double slit experiment

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An approach was made to see the double slit experiment and light refraction, different from the standard interpretation. From the light perspective, both slit and medium appear to be the same with different wave phase that is made by the coupling of complex energy. The mass and momentum are specific to the matter wave that is made by the energy separated from its conjugate, and it determines the wave phase of the space in the medium. The wave phase is supposed to change depending on the distance between the energy conjugates. As a result, when the light wave passes through the medium, it experiences a phase shift. This phase shift gives rise to the retardation and advance of wavefunction as keeping the speed of wave to be the same, and thus the speed of light remains the same regardless of the medium.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Light wave

Light is considered to be a plane wave without consideration of electromagnetism for simplicity, which corresponds to the equivalent energy and momentum of E_c and p_c . From the dispersion relation of $\omega^2 = c^2 k^2$, a wave that travels at the speed of c experiences no phase change while traveling, which implies that the phase remains a constant unless the speed of light is changed. The motion of ψ_c and ψ_c^* are the same unless the phase changes, which gives no phase offset. However, the wave conjugates take the opposite path as passing through the space of a different phase, which gives rise to the phase shift that brings a time shift between two mediums, as shown in 1.

$$\Delta t^+ = -\frac{\theta}{2\pi} \frac{1}{f} \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t^- = +\frac{\theta}{2\pi} \frac{1}{f} \quad (1)$$

As a result, the light wave experiences a time difference between ψ_c and ψ_c^* , which is equal to $2|\Delta t|$, and it is equivalent to the distance shift along the light path. It shows how the light gets slow down and makes the refraction angle as moving into the other material.

B. Charge wave

Although it is about the wave superposition, a single wave is discussed for the explanation of charge for simplicity. With wavefunctions expressed by $\psi_n^+ = A_m e^{i\frac{1}{\hbar} p_n(x-ct)}$ and $\psi_n^- = A_m e^{-i\frac{1}{\hbar} p_n(x-ct)}$, the coupling wave of wavefunctions that are separated by the space Δx is expressed by the equation of 2. With wavefunction with the same polarity, it is supposed to be a superposition by $\Psi^+ = \sum_n \psi_n^+$ and $\Psi^- = \sum_n \psi_n^-$ that appear to

FIG. 1. (a) A light state: radiation of light. (b) A charge state: wavefunctions of the same polarity are separated by the space Δx that determines the wave phase.

be a charge.

$$\psi_n^+ + \psi_n^- = 2e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar} m_n c^2 t} \cos k_n(x-ct) \cos k_n \frac{\Delta x}{\lambda} \pi \quad (2)$$

With the distance $\Delta x = 0$, it becomes a simple wave with an attenuation of $A_m = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar} m_n c^2 t}$, and it is supposed to propagate through the space by $m_n = 0$ that is equivalent to the massless wave. As the distance increases, the state of wavefunction gets away from the state of light, and the wave phase increases corresponding to the distance Δx in Fig. 1, which becomes the wave phase θ of the medium.

II. DOUBLE-SLIT EXPERIMENT

A double-slit is used to show the duality of wave and particle, but the experiment does not show the duality of quantum particle since it shows only the wave property of nature in fact, regardless of the detection available or not. Here is the explanation of this experiment, how the interference happens or not.

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FIG. 2. (a) An interference of electron's wavefunction Ψ^+/Ψ^- with light wave ψ_c/ψ_c^* and (b) with light wave ψ_c .

A. Wavefunction collapse

From the quantum mechanical view, there is a wavefunction collapse on the screen, which corresponds to the quantum measurement. It was regarded as a wavefunction collapse of light, but it is a collapse of the electron's wavefunction in fact by the interference with light wave. In order to understand this experiment, it is necessary to define the wavefunction collapse. A wavefunction is supposed to describe a wave superposition that appears to show a particle-like behavior, and the wavefunction happens to collapse by the measurement that is made by the interference with other wave. In double-slit, the position of electron is specified by the interference with the light, which is the wavefunction collapse, as shown in Fig. 2.

By the interference with an incoming light ψ_c , the position of wave packet within a wave superposition is rearranged by the change of relative distance between the packets, and it goes to x'_1 from x_1 with the wave packet that is fixed at x_0 as a reference although packets move relatively.

For the electron to be measured, there should be interferences both of the wave superposition of Ψ^+ and Ψ^- with the light wave of ψ_c and ψ_c^* , which gives rise to the position of wave packet measurable.

In double-slit, the position of wave packet appears to be a length shift that determines the light path to the screen, which indicates that whether the interference pattern appears or not is determined by the availability of light path. In other words, in order for the interference pattern to appear, the path of light wavefunction ψ_c should be consistent with the path of ψ_c^* after passing through the slit, which is equivalent to time shift by the interference from the equation 1.

If the path of ψ_c is not consistent with ψ_c^* , it becomes an unmeasurable state and makes no interference pattern on the screen. The wavefunction collapse that is expressed by the modulus squared is only possible when a pair of Ψ_c^- and Ψ_c^+ comes in simultaneity at the same path, where Ψ_c^+ and Ψ_c^- are the collapsed wavefunction of electron by the interference with light in the slit.

FIG. 3. (a) The light path is determined by the wave phase of slits s_1 and s_2 . (b) The conjugate wavefunction of ψ_1 and ψ_1^* are separated by the interference with the wavefunction of electron of wave phase.

B. Issue #1: single photon

By passing through slits s_1 and s_2 in Fig. 3, the path of wavefunction ψ_1^* is consistent with ψ_1 by the length shift due to the phase that determines the light path. In other words, the light path is determined by Δx of the corresponding medium, and the light happens to appear by the condition of $\Delta x = 2\frac{\theta}{2\pi}\lambda$, where θ is the phase specific to the slit. Otherwise, there is no light path made, and then no light comes out.

The number of photons is attributed to the light path that is made by the coupling wave in the equation 2 of the different m_n and p_n that is specific in the slit, and it appears the interference pattern on the screen followed by the corresponding path, and it is expressed by the modulus squared of Ψ_c^+ and Ψ_c^- that is the resultant wave of photons that interferes with the wave superposition of electron in the slit. It implies that the interference is not made by the light itself, but appears by the wavefunction collapse of electron, which gives a logical explanation of the interference by single photon.

C. Issue #2: which way problem

It sometimes brings a consciousness problem that is the most mysterious phenomenon of nature. To understand this mystery, a concept of complex wave is also used. The point resides in the wavefunction collapse of electron as well, not a photon. Whether the interference appears or not definitely depends on the collapse of electron's wavefunction with the light, which is a measuring action.

As previously mentioned, the slit is regarded as a wavefunction that is not determined yet before the measurement, and the state of the slit is determined by the interference with the light. Firstly, the presence of detection-
On brings a different interference wave to the slit, and the light passing through the slit s_2 is not consistent with the light through the slit s_1 in Fig. 4. As a result, with the light of ψ_2 and ψ_2^* passing through different slits s_1 and s_2 , wavefunction ψ_2 takes a different path from ψ_2^* that

FIG. 4. The detector is supposed to change the phase of conjugate wave ψ_2 , which results in light off on the screen.

is equivalent to the delayed time, and there is no light path made and no light on the screen. In other words, ψ_2 going through slit s_2 is supposed to be interfered by the presence of the detection, and there is no wavefunction of ψ_2 and ψ_2^* at the same time on the screen. With the detector-Off, ψ_2^* is not supposed to be interfered by the detection, and then it enables the light path to the screen, by which a wavefunction ψ and ψ^* reaches on the screen at the same time, and light comes out, which gives rise to an interference pattern of the double-slit.

On the other hand, by passing through the same slit, the path of a wavefunction ψ_1 is consistent with the ψ_1^* as satisfying $\Delta x = 2\frac{\theta}{2\pi}\lambda$, by which the light path is enabled, and the light comes on the screen. It happens to bring a diffraction pattern on the screen by a single slit, and thus there is a diffraction pattern only available with the detection On .

III. REFRACTION

In the group velocity theory, it is explained by the wave superposition with the secondary wave that is made by the excitation of electron by the incoming light. Following this, the light should pass through the medium like a water at the same time as the air, without a delay although it creates a wave superposition inside the medium. Unfortunately, it does not happen, and the light reaches with a delay in the water.

A. Wave separation by phase shift

The light path is also applied for the explanation of light refraction. Different from the free space, a phase

shift appears in the vicinity of wavefunctions of ψ_n^+ and ψ_n^- with the mass m_n and momentum p_n separated by the space, which is found in the medium like the water or glass, even in the metal like a germanium.

When the light comes into the different medium, the light wave experiences a phase shift depending on the coupling wave of 2 with the mass m_n and momentum p_n that are specific to the medium. By passing through the medium, the wavefunctions of light are separated by the

FIG. 5. A time shift of incoming light takes place at each coupling wave, which results in the time delay of light.

phase shift corresponding to 1, and then the total time shift is summed up till the end of the medium as shown in Fig. 5.

B. Time delay

The speed of wave remains the same regardless of the phase difference. However, it experiences a time advance and retardation of conjugate wavefunctions of ψ_c and ψ_c^* due to the phase shift in the medium. From the equation 1, there comes a time delay of the wave due to the phase shift inside a medium, and the delayed time Δt passing through the medium becomes as follows :

$$\delta t = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\theta}{2\pi} \lambda = \frac{\theta}{2\pi} \frac{1}{f} \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t = 2n\delta t = \frac{n\theta}{\pi} \frac{1}{f} \quad (3)$$

which is the total time delay that is made by the interference between light and charge waves of the medium, where n is the number of coupling waves in the path of light.